

How to order a LEGO™ demonstrator

The individual pieces can be purchased via the official LEGO™ website available in your country. From the menu, select “Shop” and then “Bricks and Pieces” (or whatever they translate to in the local language). Alternatively, the site BrickLink.com is the largest online marketplace for the reselling of Lego™ items and pieces can be purchased there.

Ordering from the LEGO™ website

You can either search for the pieces using the item number and add them to your basket. Sometimes a piece can have multiple associated item numbers and if the part is not found, try an alternative item number as stated in the models’ parts list. Alternatively, you can download the .csv file associated with the model and then upload it directly to the website by selecting “Upload List”.

Sometimes pieces may not be available so always check your basket against a parts list and replace any missing pieces with alternatively coloured versions.

Ordering from BrickLink.com

Here you can search for the individual pieces using the item number and order them from third parties. You can also access the designs directly, download their source files, and add the pieces to a “Wanted List”.

Some issues with “ID”s and “Item No”s and other differences between LEGO™ and Bricklink.com

LEGO™’s website refers to part numbers as their ID and Bricklink.com uses an Item Number system. Often the number listed on Bricklink.com may not correspond to an available part on LEGO™’s site. For example, a 1x1 round plate:

On Bricklink.com, this is listed primarily as part 4073, with its LEGO™ ID of 6141, listed later.

Sometimes these alternative item numbers on Bricklink.com can refer to different colours of the same pieces listed on **LEGO™**'s site. For example, a 1x1 plate is listed as two separate numbers on **LEGO™**'s site, depending on whether the piece is translucent.

[Catalog](#): [Parts](#): [Plate](#): 3024

Plate 1 x 1

Item No: 3024 Alternate Item No: 28554, 30008, 63326

Select Color

Item Info

Years Released: 1962 - 2026
Weight: 0.2g
Stud Dim.: 1 x 1 in studs
Pack. Dim.: 0.8 x 0.8 x 0.51 cm

Item Consists Of

N/A

My Store Inventory

[Add to My Store Inventory](#)
262734 Lots For Sale

My Wanted List

[Add to My Wanted List](#)
On 6312485 Wanted Lists

Q plate 1x1

560 results

Sort By Filter

PLATE 1X1

Color swatches: yellow, grey, orange, blue, white (9)

ID: 28554

£0.05

PLATE 1X1

Color swatches: teal, white, blue, orange, green (44)

ID: 3024

£0.05

Pieces that are near-identical are not listed together on Bricklink.com. For example, if you were to search for 4459 on **LEGO™**'s site, it does not exist.

[Catalog](#): [Parts](#): [Technic](#), [Pin](#): 4459

Technic, Pin with Long Friction Ridges

Item No: 4459

Select Color

Uh-oh! '4459' didn't bring up any results.

[Clear Search](#)

However, this is a very common **LEGO™** TECHNIC piece, so it definitely should be available. To find the correct code, you can look to related items and try those numbers.

Catalog: Parts: Technic, Pin: 4459

Technic, Pin with Long Friction Ridges
Item No: 4459

Select Color

Related Items:

This Item is a mold variant of the following Item(s):

- Part [2780](#) Technic, Pin with Short Friction Ridges
- Part [3673](#) Technic, Pin without Friction Ridges

Catalog: Parts: Technic, Pin: 2780

Technic, Pin with Short Friction Ridges
Item No: 2780 Alternate Item No: 61332

Select Color

TECHNIC

CONNECTOR PEG W. FRICTION

■ (1)

ID: 61332

£0.06

Colours are also listed differently between the two sites. In the notes for each design, I list first **LEGO™**'s colour name, and then Bricklink.com's if it differs.

Tweaking a design

You must first download and install Bricklink.com's program "[Studio](#)" from their website.

Then download the .io file for the design you wish to tweak and open the "Studio" app. In the app, select "Open file".

Then select the file you downloaded. The app should then look something like this:

Now you can change the piece colours or other aspects of the design.

There are many tutorials available online, so that may be a good place to start if it does not feel intuitive.

Images: All images are either from **LEGO**TM's sites, Bricklink.com, or have been generated by the document author using Bricklink.com's "Studio" software.